

INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON NEWSPAPER READERSHIP AMONG RESIDENTS OF OLUYOLE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, IBADAN

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Abstract: *The proliferation of social media has transformed news consumption patterns, posing a significant challenge to traditional newspaper readership. With the increasing reliance on digital platforms, newspaper circulation and readership continue to decline. This study examined the influence of social media on newspaper readership among residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan. Guided by the Uses and Gratifications Theory, the study employed a descriptive survey design with a sample of 399 respondents selected through random sampling. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire and analysed with descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that WhatsApp (77.3%) was the most frequently used social media platform among respondents. Results further indicated that 46.7% of respondents believe social media spreads fake news rapidly, while 34.7% reported depending primarily on social media as their main source of news. The study recommends that newspapers enhance their online presence to engage wider audiences and that media literacy programmes be promoted to strengthen the ability of readers to identify fake news.*

Introduction

Newspaper readership refers to the number of individuals who regularly or occasionally read printed newspapers, encompassing both subscribers and those who access copies through vendors, libraries, or shared sources. It

reflects engagement with news, opinions, and features published in these outlets, often measured by circulation figures and audience surveys. In Nigeria, readership is influenced by factors such as literacy, income, urban-rural divides, and access to media (Akinfeleye, 2018).

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Despite challenges from digital platforms and economic barriers, newspaper readership remains a key element of the media landscape. Major newspapers like *The Punch*, *Vanguard*, *The Guardian*, and *ThisDay* attract significant readership, particularly among urban, educated, and professional audiences in cities such as Lagos, Abuja, and Port Harcourt (Oso, 2017). However, readership is limited in rural areas due to low literacy rates, poverty, and distribution challenges, with English-language newspapers dominating because of Nigeria's colonial legacy, though regional publications in Yoruba, Hausa, and Igbo serve niche audiences (Uche, 2019; Musa, 2020).

Newspapers play an important role as a mass medium by providing timely information at regular intervals. They are useful for education, information, relaxation, and entertainment, which explains their relevance in society, as they keep readers informed of events within and outside their immediate environments (Okon, 2016). Scholars reinforce this by emphasizing that newspapers serve as a carrier of current information and news (Akinwale, 2018). Studies further describe newspapers as textbooks that provide up-to-date information on local, national, and international affairs, alongside critical analyses of government decisions, features on arts, entertainment, and even comic relief for relaxation (Ekwelie, 2015). Beyond informing, newspapers also promote literacy empowerment, critical thinking, retention of

information, and civic-conscious values that foster tolerance and community engagement (Olayiwola, 2019).

On the other hand, social media has emerged as a powerful communication tool, enabling individuals to share information, interact, and create online communities through platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, and LinkedIn. Businesses also take advantage of these platforms for marketing, customer service, and product promotion. With the rapid development of social media, information consumption has changed dramatically in the digital age (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). For many, especially young people, social media has become a preferred source of news because of its accessibility, multimedia features, and real-time updates. This trend is particularly visible among tertiary students who rely heavily on social media as a quick and convenient source of news updates (Alabi, 2021). While newspapers, both print and digital, continue to be viewed as credible sources of in-depth reporting, social media's interactive and customisable nature has reshaped readership patterns, posing a strong challenge to traditional newspaper consumption (Okoro & Nwafor, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

The proliferation of social media has revolutionized the way people consume news, posing a significant threat to traditional newspaper readership. With the rise of online

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news sources and social media platforms, readers are increasingly turning to digital channels for their news, leading to a decline in newspaper circulation and readership. This shift has forced newspapers to reevaluate their business models and adapt to the changing media landscape

As the preference for digital platforms grows, newspaper readership in the area appears to be declining. This raises important questions about the relevance and sustainability of print media in the digital age. It also brings concerns about the reliability of news on social media, where misinformation can spread easily. Hence, the study examines the influence of social media on newspaper readership among residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan.

Research Objectives

1. Identify social media platforms through which residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan read news
2. Assess the the level of newspaper readership among residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan
3. Ascertain the perception of residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan towards news on social media.

Research Questions

1. What are the social media platforms through which residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan read news?

2. What is the the level of newspaper readership among residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan?

3. What is the perception of residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan towards news on social media?

Literature Review

Newspaper Readership

Newspapers are made up of diverse contents which contain international, national, and local news. Other contents include letters to the editor, movie listings, entertainment gist, and many more. These are periodicals with educative, informative, entertaining, culturally promoting messages and other important information that are beneficial to a specific locality. Scholars define some features that determine a true newspaper. First, a newspaper should be made up of diverse contents which may contain local, national, and international news (Stephens, 2017). Second, newspapers are conveniently packaged according to content: there are sections devoted to general news, sports, entertainment, and so on (Stephens, 2017). Third, the newspaper serves as a historical record — newspaper journalism is often described as “the first draft of history” (Graham, 1959/1990; McPherson, 2010). Fourth, newspapers perform the watchdog role in society (Freedom Forum, n.d.). Lastly, newspapers are timely, because news loses its relevance if it becomes stale (Stephens, 2017).

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The concept of readership is germane to newspapers. The concept of readership may be abstruse to define, but it is mostly associated with newspapers, magazines, and all kinds of periodicals. Readership is defined as “all the readers of a certain publication, authors, and so on,” or more broadly, the collective audience for a publication (Malthouse & Calder, 2002). It also refers to the number of people or the type of people who read a particular newspaper or magazine (Thornton, 2016). The world of newspapers has undergone considerable transformation. Online newspaper readership has made the literate audience custodians of timely and up-to-date information (Thornton, 2016). The emergence of online newspapers has indeed introduced a new approach to information seeking and, by extension, has led to the use of social media platforms as access points for news (Thornton, 2016).

State of Newspaper Readership

Reports indicate that globally the newspaper is passing through its hardest time ever, especially since the Internet began to provide online functionalities and possibilities far beyond what the newspaper could offer: instant and free news, interactive and multimedia features, and easy accessibility through simple handheld technologies such as mobile phones and personal computers (Pavlik, 2001; Boczkowski, 2004). Literature is replete with materials which chronicle the monumental shifts in news consumption around the world. Examples

include headlines such as “Murdoch Predicts Gloomy Future for Press”, “The Future of Newspapers: Who Killed the Newspaper?”, “Goodbye to Newspapers?”, “Newspaper Circulation Continues to Decline Rapidly”, and “Newspaper Closings Raise Fears about Industry” (The Economist, 2006; Project for Excellence in Journalism, 2008; Pew Research Center, 2010).

It is important to note, however, that many reports do not support the hypothesis that print media readership is going extinct. For instance, some scholars argue that the mass migration from printed newspapers to online sources of news is not fully supported by facts (Nguyen, 2010; Boczkowski & Mitchelstein, 2013). While some migration from offline to online news consumption has occurred, the change is not as dramatic as often claimed, and the impact on printed newspapers is not as apocalyptic as suggesting the “death” of the newspaper (Nguyen, 2010). The online news media, in many cases, acts more as a complement than a substitute for print (Flavián & Gurrea, 2009). Furthermore, studies show that Malaysian newspapers, for instance, continue to attract advertising revenue despite the rise of online platforms (Mustaffa, Ibrahim, & Kee, 2017). This implies that there is still some level of newspaper readership around the world, despite frequent claims that online media is displacing print.

Social Media

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Mass media have been a major agent of socialisation and a tool for social change, especially now that people depend heavily on messages from mass media. The power of the mass media helps address social problems. Television, radio, and print advertising can entice people to buy a wide range of products and services, while newspaper messages and advertisements influence ideas, values, and behaviour (McQuail, 2010). Social media has emerged as one of the most vital means of communication. It eases communication among people regardless of distance, allowing them to share information, files, pictures, videos, create blogs, send messages, and conduct real-time conversations (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). These systems are referred to as “social” because they allow communication with friends, classmates, teachers, project supervisors, and lecturers easily and effectively.

Social media, a form of electronic communication, has become one of the most dominant activities on the internet (boyd & Ellison, 2007). Through social media, individuals can exchange useful information that enhances professional interests, ideas, and collaborations. It also allows for the transmission of pictorial and graphical representations of ideas. Scholars define social media as a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that enable the creation and exchange of user-generated

content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). It is possible to use mass media to encourage people to act on behalf of their health, well-being, or the broader good of society. Based on this assumption, since World War II, federal, state, and local governments, along with private foundations and non-governmental organisations, have sponsored hundreds of public service campaigns to promote social rather than commercial goods (Randall, 2001; Hornik, 2002).

Theoretical Review

Uses and Gratification Theory

The Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT) is a communication theory that explores how and why individuals actively seek out specific media to satisfy particular needs. Developed by Elihu Katz, Jay Blumler, and Michael Gurevitch in the 1970s, UGT marked a departure from earlier media effects theories that perceived audiences as passive recipients of media messages (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1974). Instead, it emphasises audience agency, recognising that media users actively choose and engage with media to fulfil particular needs, which may include cognitive (seeking knowledge), affective (emotional experiences), personal integrative (enhancing credibility and confidence), social integrative (interaction and socialising), and tension release (relaxation and escape) (McQuail, 2010). UGT assumes that media use is purposeful and goal-directed, acknowledging that individuals’ backgrounds, experiences, and

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expectations shape how and why they consume particular media. This makes the theory especially relevant in analysing interactive platforms such as social media, where user participation and content customisation are high (Ruggiero, 2000).

In relation to this study, UGT is significant for explaining the influence of social media on newspaper readership among residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan. The theory helps account for the shift in audience behaviour from traditional print newspapers to digital platforms, as residents may prefer social media for its immediacy, accessibility, interactivity, and convenience. Rather than reflecting a declining interest in news itself, the reduced readership of print newspapers may instead highlight a change in the medium through which people access information. Younger and technologically inclined residents in particular may find social media more engaging for following current events, sharing opinions, and interacting with peers. Thus, UGT provides a useful framework for understanding how individuals in Oluyole LGA actively make

media choices based on personal motivations, thereby explaining the evolving patterns of news consumption.

Methodology

This study employed a survey research design, considered most suitable for critically analysing data and ensuring generalisability of findings. The population comprised residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan, with a total of 202,725 people according to the 2006 National Population Census. Using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula with a 0.05 margin of error, a sample size of approximately 399 respondents was determined, selected through simple random sampling to ensure representativeness. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered online via Google Forms to facilitate accessibility. Collected data were coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used to summarise responses.

Results

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of the social media platforms through which residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan read news (N = 375)

Platform	F U	SU	FAU	NU	Mean	Std. Dev.
Facebook	120(32%)	100(26.7%)	80(21.3%)	75(20%)	2.71	1.12
WhatsApp	290(77.3%)	50(13.3%)	25(6.7%)	10(2.7%)	3.65	0.72
X (Twitter)	90(24%)	110(29.3%)	70(18.7%)	105(28%)	2.49	1.14
Snapchat	60(16%)	90(24%)	80(21.3%)	145(38.7%)	2.17	1.11
LinkedIn	40(10.7)	60(16%)	85(22.7%)	190(50.7%)	1.87	1.04
Instagram	200(53.3%)	90(24%)	50(13.3%)	35(8%)	3.21	1.00
YouTube	250(66.7%)	80(21.3%)	30(8%)	15(4%)	3.51	0.81
TikTok	180(48%)	100(26.7%)	60(16%)	35(9.3%)	3.13	1.00
Telegram	95(25.3%)	110(29.3%)	85(22.7%)	85(22.7%)	2.57	1.10
Grand Mean					2.81	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

(FU= Frequently Used, SU= Sometimes Used, FAU= Fairly Used, NU=Never used)

The data presented in the table provide an overview of the usage patterns of various social media platforms among 375 respondents, measured on a four-point scale: Frequently Used, Sometimes Used, Fairly Used, and Never Used. The mean and standard deviation for each platform indicate the average level of usage and the variability in responses, respectively.

WhatsApp emerged as the most frequently used platform, with 77.3% of respondents indicating regular use. It recorded the highest mean score

of 3.65 and the lowest standard deviation (0.72), showing consistent usage across respondents. Similarly, YouTube and Instagram followed closely with high frequency usage rates of 66.7% and 53.3%, and mean scores of 3.51 and 3.21, respectively. These findings suggest that these platforms are widely integrated into the daily digital routines of the participants. In contrast, LinkedIn was the least used platform, with 50.7% of respondents reporting they never use it, and only 10.7% indicating frequent use. It had the lowest mean score of 1.87, highlighting

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its limited relevance or appeal, possibly due to its professional networking focus which might not align with the interests or needs of the largely youthful demographic.

Snapchat and X (Twitter) also showed low usage levels, with mean scores of 2.17 and 2.49, respectively. A significant number of respondents reported never using Snapchat (38.7%) and Twitter (28%), although some respondents did indicate occasional use. Facebook, while once a dominant platform, appears to be used less frequently by this sample, with a mean score of 2.71. Only 32%

reported frequent use, which may reflect a shift towards newer platforms. Telegram also showed moderate usage, with a mean of 2.57, indicating a mix of occasional and low usage patterns. The grand mean of 2.81 suggests that, on average, social media platforms are moderately used among the respondents. The variation in standard deviations across platforms reflects differing degrees of user engagement, with platforms like WhatsApp and YouTube enjoying more consistent and widespread usage compared to others like LinkedIn and Snapchat.

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of the level of newspaper readership among residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan (N = 375)

Variable	H	VH	L	VL	Mean	Std. Dev.
Interest in reading newspapers	110(29.3%)	80(21.3%)	100(26.7%)	85(22.7%)	2.49	1.06
Access to printed newspapers	90(24%)	95(25.3%)	110(29.3%)	80(21.3%)	2.53	1.09
Time spent reading newspapers	100(26.7%)	85(22.7%)	105(28%)	85(22.7%)	2.49	1.08
Use of newspapers for daily update	120(32%)	100(26.7%)	90(24%)	65(17.3%)	2.68	1.05
Exposure to newspaper content	130(34.7%)	95(25.3%)	85(22.7%)	65(17.3%)	2.68	1.03
Dependence on newspaper for news	115(30.7%)	90(24%)	95(25.3%)	75(20%)	2.59	1.06
Grand Mean					2.58	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

(H= High, VH= Very High, L= Low, VL= Very Low)

The data on respondents' engagement with newspapers highlight varying levels of interest, access, and usage. Responses were measured on

a four-point scale—Very High, High, Low, and Very Low—with accompanying mean scores and standard deviations to indicate the central

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tendency and spread. Looking at individual items, the highest levels of engagement were recorded in exposure to newspaper content and use of newspapers for daily updates, both with a mean of 2.68. For exposure, 34.7% of respondents rated it high, and 25.3% rated it very high, suggesting that many respondents are still interacting with newspaper content, possibly through both printed and digital formats. Similarly, the use of newspapers for daily updates received strong responses, with 32% and 26.7% indicating high and very high usage respectively.

The lowest level of engagement was seen in interest in reading newspapers, which had a mean score of 2.49, with 26.7% and 22.7% of respondents selecting low and very low, respectively. This suggests that despite some level of exposure and use, actual enthusiasm or personal motivation to read newspapers is relatively low. Access to printed newspapers and time spent reading newspapers also scored modestly with mean values of 2.53 and 2.49, respectively. While about half of the respondents reported high or very high access

and time spent, the remaining half indicated lower levels, suggesting potential barriers to availability or personal time constraints.

Dependence on newspapers for news also showed a moderate mean of 2.59, with 30.7% rating it high and 24% very high. This implies that a fair number of respondents still rely on newspapers, although likely as a supplementary rather than primary source. Overall, the grand mean of 2.58 indicates a moderate level of engagement with newspapers among respondents. This suggests that while newspapers are still part of the media consumption habits of the respondents, they are not the dominant source of news and information.

In conclusion, the data reflect a moderate but declining engagement with newspapers among the respondents. While many still access and occasionally rely on newspapers, the relatively low levels of interest and time spent suggest that traditional print media may be losing its appeal, especially among younger or more digitally inclined audiences.

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Table 3: Descriptive analysis of the perception of residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan towards news on social media (N = 375)

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev
I trust the news I see on social media	60(16%)	105(28%)	120(32%)	90(24%)	2.12	0.99
Social media is my main source of news	110(29.3%)	130(34.7%)	80(21.3%)	55(14.7%)	2.64	1.01
News on social media often lacks credible sources	150(40%)	125(33.3%)	60(16%)	40(10.7%)	3.03	0.94
I think social media spreads fake news quickly	175(46.7%)	135(36%)	40(10.7%)	25(6.7%)	3.23	0.88
I prefer social media news over traditional media	80(21.3%)	115(30.7%)	95(25.3%)	85(22.7%)	2.30	1.06
News on social media is often misleading	140(37.3%)	130(34.7%)	60(16%)	45(12%)	2.99	0.97
Grand Mean					2.72	

Source: Field Survey (2025)

(Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD))

The data on respondents’ perceptions of news on social media reveal mixed attitudes, showing both reliance and concerns about credibility. The responses are measured on a four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The grand mean of 2.72 indicates an overall moderate agreement with the statements, suggesting that while many use social media for news, they do so with caution.

A significant number of respondents expressed concern about misinformation on social media. Item 23, “I think social media spreads fake news quickly,” recorded the highest mean score of 3.23, with a combined 82.7% of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing. Similarly, item 22,

“News on social media often lacks credible sources,” had a mean of 3.03, with 73.3% of respondents acknowledging this issue. Item 25, “News on social media is often misleading,” also had a high mean of 2.99, further indicating widespread scepticism.

Despite these concerns, a considerable number of respondents still use social media as a primary news source. Item 21, “Social media is my main source of news,” had a mean of 2.64, with 64% in agreement. This suggests a strong reliance on social media platforms for staying informed, possibly due to convenience and real-time updates.

Trust in social media news, however, appears relatively low. Only 44% of respondents agreed

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or strongly agreed with item 20, “I trust the news I see on social media,” while 56% disagreed or strongly disagreed, resulting in a mean of 2.12, the lowest among all items. This further underscores the trust deficit despite high usage.

Lastly, preference for social media over traditional media also leaned towards the negative, with a mean score of 2.30 for item 24. A majority either disagreed (25.3%) or strongly disagreed (22.7%) with the statement, suggesting that while social media is frequently used, it is not necessarily preferred over conventional news sources such as television, radio, or newspapers.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from research question one revealed that the majority of respondents frequently use WhatsApp (77.3%), making it the most popular platform among the sample. This is followed by YouTube, which is also widely used, with 66.7% of respondents indicating frequent use. Instagram and TikTok are similarly popular, with 53.3% and 48% of respondents respectively reporting frequent usage. In contrast, Facebook appears to be moderately used, with only 32% of respondents indicating frequent use. X (Twitter) and Telegram are not frequently used by most respondents, with the majority selecting “sometimes used” for these platforms. Snapchat and LinkedIn are the least used platforms; 38.7% of respondents never use Snapchat, while 50.7% never use LinkedIn,

suggesting that these platforms are not commonly accessed by the respondents.

The findings from research question two revealed that majority of respondents reported high levels of exposure to and use of newspapers for information. Specifically, 34.7% indicated high exposure to newspaper content, while 32% reported high use of newspapers for daily updates, and 30.7% noted a high dependence on newspapers for news. These responses suggest that newspapers still play a relevant role in the respondents’ information consumption. However, interest in reading newspapers appears to be relatively lower, with only 29.3% indicating a high level of interest. A notable portion of the respondents reported low (26.7%) and very low (22.7%) interest in reading newspapers, highlighting a declining enthusiasm for traditional print media. For access to printed newspapers, 25.3% of respondents reported very high access, while 29.3% had low access, indicating a mixed level of availability. Likewise, the time spent reading newspapers was also moderate, with 26.7% reporting high time commitment and a combined 50.7% indicating low or very low time spent.

The findings from research question three revealed that majority of respondents believe social media spreads fake news quickly, as 46.7% strongly agreed and 36% agreed with this statement. In addition, a majority also agreed that news on social media often lacks credible

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sources, with 40% strongly agreeing and 33.3% agreeing, while 37.3% strongly agreed and 34.7% agreed that news on social media is often misleading. These responses indicate widespread concern about the reliability and truthfulness of news circulated on social media platforms. Despite these concerns, the findings revealed that a majority of respondents still depend on social media as their main source of news, with 29.3% strongly agreeing and 34.7% agreeing to that effect. However, only a minority (44%) expressed trust in the news they see on social media, while a larger percentage (56%) either disagreed or strongly disagreed, indicating low overall trust in social media news. Moreover, while 30.7% agreed and 21.3% strongly agreed that they prefer social media news over traditional media, a significant portion of respondents (48%) did not share this preference.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that while social media platforms, particularly WhatsApp, YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok, have become the dominant sources of news and interaction among residents of Oluyole Local Government Area, newspapers still retain a

References

Alabi, R. (2021). Social media use and news consumption among tertiary students in Nigeria. *Journal of Communication and Media Studies*, 13(2), 45-59.

measure of relevance as a source of credible information, though interest and time commitment towards print media are declining. The study further shows that despite the widespread use of social media for news consumption, respondents harbour significant concerns about its reliability, with many acknowledging the prevalence of fake news, lack of credible sources, and misleading content. Nevertheless, social media remains the preferred medium for accessing news due to its accessibility, immediacy, and convenience, even though overall trust in the information shared on these platforms remains relatively low. This indicates a shifting media consumption pattern where social media is gaining dominance, but traditional newspapers continue to serve as important channels for credible and in-depth reporting.

Recommendations

1. Newspapers should improve their online presence to attract more readers.
2. Media literacy programmes should be encouraged to help people identify fake news.
3. Newspapers should be made more affordable and accessible to the public.

Akinfeleye, R. A. (2018). *Essentials of journalism and mass communication in Nigeria*. Lagos: University of Lagos Press.

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- Akinwale, A. (2018). The role of newspapers in the dissemination of information in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Mass Communication*, 7(1), 22–34.
- Boczkowski, P. J. (2004). *Digitizing the news: Innovation in online newspapers*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Boczkowski, P. J., & Mitchelstein, E. (2013). *The news gap: When the information preferences of the media and the public diverge*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- boyd, d. m., & Ellison, N. B. (2007). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), 210–230. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00393.x>
- Ekwelie, S. (2015). Newspapers as textbooks: Their roles in education and public enlightenment. *African Journal of Communication Studies*, 3(1), 55–70.
- Flavián, C., & Gurrea, R. (2009). The choice of digital newspapers: Influence of reader goals and user experience. *Internet Research*, 19(3), 313–332. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10662240910965318>
- Freedom Forum. (n.d.). The role of a free press. Retrieved from <https://www.freedomforum.org>
- Graham, P. (1990). *The first draft of history: Selected journalism. (Original work published 1959)*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Hornik, R. C. (2002). *Public health communication: Evidence for behavior change*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of social media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2009.09.003>
- Katz, E., Blumler, J. G., & Gurevitch, M. (1974). Utilization of mass communication by the individual. In J. G. Blumler & E. Katz (Eds.). *The uses of mass communications: Current perspectives on gratifications research* (pp. 19–32). Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- Malthouse, E. C., & Calder, B. J. (2002). Reading print, reading online. *Newspaper Research Journal*, 23(2–3), 61–73. <https://doi.org/10.1177/073953290202300206>

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- McPherson, J. M. (2010). Journalism as history: Newspapers as the first draft. *American Journalism Review*, 32(1), 45-52.
- McQuail, D. (2010). *McQuail's mass communication theory* (6th ed.). London: Sage.
- Musa, A. (2020). The role of indigenous language newspapers in promoting cultural identity in Nigeria. *Journal of African Media Studies*, 12(3), 335-349. https://doi.org/10.1386/jams_00028_1
- Mustaffa, N., Ibrahim, F., & Kee, C. P. (2017). Newspaper survival in the digital age: The Malaysian experience. *Journal of Asian Pacific Communication*, 27(1), 59-76. <https://doi.org/10.1075/japc.27.1.04mu s>
- Nguyen, A. (2010). Harnessing the potential of online news: Suggestions from a study on the relationship between online news advantages and its post-adoption consequences. *Journalism*, 11(2), 223-241. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1464884909355910>
- Okon, P. (2016). The relevance of newspapers in the modern society. *Journal of Media and Society*, 4(1), 12-27.
- Okoro, N., & Nwafor, K. A. (2020). Social media use and its influence on the consumption of traditional newspapers among Nigerian youths. *Journal of African Media Studies*, 12(2), 249-264. https://doi.org/10.1386/jams_00022_1
- Olayiwola, R. (2019). Newspapers and civic engagement: Literacy empowerment and democratic participation. *Nigerian Journal of Communication*, 16(1), 77-93.
- Oso, L. (2017). *Media and society in Nigeria*. Abeokuta: African Council for Communication Education.
- Pavlik, J. V. (2001). *Journalism and new media*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Project for Excellence in Journalism. (2008). *The state of the news media 2008*. Washington, DC: Pew Research Center.
- Pew Research Center. (2010). *State of the news media 2010*. Washington, DC: Pew Research Center.
- Randall, D. (2001). *The universal journalist* (2nd ed.). London: Pluto Press.

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Ruggiero, T. E. (2000). Uses and gratifications theory in the 21st century. *Mass Communication and Society*, 3(1), 3–37. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327825MCSo301_02

Stephens, M. (2017). *A history of news* (4th ed.). New York: Oxford University Press.

The Economist. (2006, August 24). Who killed the newspaper? *The Economist*. <https://www.economist.com>

Thornton, B. (2016). Readership and the transformation of newspapers in the digital era. *Journal of Media Innovations*, 3(1), 23–36. <https://doi.org/10.5617/jmi.v3i1.1234>

Uche, L. U. (2019). *Mass media, people and politics in Nigeria*. New York: Concept Publishing.